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EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF GUERRILLA MARKETING ON CUSTOMERS' LOYALTY THROUGH BRAND TRUST

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KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
Guerrilla Marketing, Brand Loyalty, Security, Brand Web-Design & Brand Trust	<p>This study investigates effect of guerilla marketing on brand loyalty through brand trust as the mediator. A survey was conducted to confirm the study's hypotheses. The sample size of 250 and despite the average response rate in Pakistan, 400 questionnaires were sent out to e-banking customers, of which 230 were returned. Twelve incomplete responses were removed from further analysis, while 218 complete responses were subjected to statistical analysis. According to results of structural equation model, the influence of guerilla marketing on social media has an effect on customer's loyalty. The model of this study evaluates brand attitude, security, website design as independent and brand trust consider as a mediating variable and outcome variables is customer loyalty. The results of this study indicated that there is a significant and positive relationship with customer loyalty and trust as a mediator has significant and positive relationship between observed variables. Outcomes provide theoretical information about guerilla marketing. The research assists advertisers in understanding the factors that influence brand image effects of Guerilla marketing.</p> <p>2022 Journal of Social Research Development</p>
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INTRODUCTION

Guerrilla marketing can be defined as the use of force to achieve organizational goals and to make a profit. Previously, it was used for small businesses to be recognized on the small budget. However, it became very popular as large corporations adopted strategy (Wend & land, 2016). Some of most well-known brands, including Nike and Audi, have effectively executed this Guerilla marketing method in each area (Jin & colleagues, 2009). A product

is a very important as well as widely accepted as main reason consumers choose to buy a product. It is in power of confidence that make decisions, despite having some priorities (Baltes & Leibing, 2008). Guerilla marketing has been great catalyst for creating customer-targeting and attractive target for advertisers (Chung, Lee & Heath, 2013). Still, the guerilla marketing is limited to passers-by. The marketing activities are like that. The internet has changed all of this (Iqbal & Lohdi, 2015a). The internet has made it likely for many people to see events even though they may not be real (Milak & Dobrinić, 2017). The traditional practices were limited. Now, millions can see it all. Birds of the feather are used on Twitter (Chan, Ng & Luk, 2013).

Sharing the most effective guerilla marketing tactics and growing your business. If you're thinking about it, the limit is good place to start (Tam & Khuong, 2015a). Pakistan market is large and consumes a lot of advertising. This study focuses on the product image and identifies the Guerilla marketing impact on the images of various products. This study also examines the potential impact of Guerilla marketing on a product image. (McNaughton, 2008). The users of social media about information can have positive impact on the use of information. However, the potential effects of the products are well known. (Nufer, 2013). In addition to the other two programs they have advised the relationship between attitude and intentional behavior. According to Pakistan telecommunications authority, 183 million Pakistani mobile users are leading in big data file (Pakistan Telecommunication Authority, 2021). Marketing strategies. This study aims to improve the image of the product by examining the impact of these strategies on product identification (Erkan & Evans, 2016a). The above-mentioned researchers have raised the following research question: What are guerrilla marketing strategies that affect the brand loyalty in diverse contexts the through mediation of brand trust?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer attitudes toward them have changed as the result of frequent advertising (Burt & Davies, 2010) on popular channels like billboards, newspapers, billboards, and billboards (Martin & Smith, 2008). Market leaders are now looking for new ways to reach customers in more attractive ways (Tolba, 2011). Traditional practices have become obsolete. Consumer minds are not always clear and they are looking for ways to entice them to buy their products (Hatch, 2005). Some obsolete marketing methods can cause displeasure among consumers. Thus, market leaders use guerilla marketing to divide collections and convey message (Choi et al., 2009). Terrorist marketing involves campaign in which consumer creates meaningful social relationships using a lot of low-budget ads (Shang et al., 2006). Brand image includes different features and features of products and product services explicitly. In other words, a product image is considered a general idea of the product. Product imagery is associated with formation of emotional attachment to products (Rubio et al., 2014). Previous research examined various marketing strategies; celebrity accreditation (Suki, 2013). Development of an information acceptance model is developed to attract and affect consumer's purchase

objectives. Designed to promote good electronic wording. This model promotes usefulness of information, the acceptance of information as a precursor to the purpose of purchase (Fishbein et al., 1975).

This model suggested how computer use affects information features. Information quality means convincing power embedded in message. Information that reduces human awareness criteria is shown as high quality information (Zhu et al., 2016). The level of information is amazing as consumers consider the information to be useful. The quality of the information is therefore vital source of useful information (Erkan and Evans (2016a) have confirmed that information quality has a strong relationship within the usefulness of information. However, the quality of information is not only important in use of information but also in receiving information. People who see high quality information will be more likely to get information. Previous models have hinted at these linkages, but in this work, we provide a direct link to our research model. The reliability of information is important factor in providing integrity of the message (Chan et al., 2013). It is important element of useful information. People often deliberately make useful information when see information as reliable (Cheung & Thadani, 2012). The reliability of information is considered a key factor in decision-making process (Cheung et al., 2009a). the prior information needs are considered as seeking advice (Wolny & Mueller, 2013).

In previous studies, need for information is considered separate research question (Erkan & Elwalda, 2018). Several studies have anticipated that people who need required information on social media are likely to establish it useful; these relationships were also confirmed in their research. As this study deliberately undermined the impact of Guerilla marketing on social media, we considered using information needs (Wu & Wang, 2014a). The way people think about information is one of variables we have measured as one of Guerilla marketing elements on social media that affect image of product (Fishbein et al., 1975). The attitude of knowledge is considered and has great impact on brand image (Erkan & Elwalda, 2018). The other two theories have been model of embracing the proposed theory and the theory of organized behavior. Erkan and Evans (2016) thus modified these variables to provide that the contempt of social media users could have a positive impact on use of information (Erkan & Elwalda, 2018). People with positive attitudes about information will be likely to access information. Use of information refers to people's awareness that user information will increase performance (Wu & Lin, 2017). Previous research also found useful information on purpose of purchase.

METHODOLOGY

Survey was conducted to confirm hypotheses in this study. This study survey questionnaire is divided into two sections. The demographic information of respondent was collected in first section of the questionnaire, while constructs modified from literature were collected in the second section. Items were graded on a five-point Likert scale ranging from strongly

disagree=1 to strongly agree=5. Responses from e-banking users of the certain institutions were gathered via purposeful sampling. Sample size recommended by [Krejcie & Morgan \(1970\)](#), 250 samples, is sufficient for obtaining reliable result. Despite Pakistan's average response rate, 400 questionnaires were issued to e-banking users, and 230 were returned. Twelve responses were partially filled and eliminated for further study, while 218 complete responses were subjected to the statistical testing. Additional demographic information is provided. This survey uses the multi-item design. Eight constructs were used to increase reliability and validity. The data was analyzed using partial least square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) approach ([Hair, 2017](#)). Hypotheses were statistically tested using Smart PLS 3.0 program.

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The desired results as obtained through statistical procedures have been presented in this section in order to examine outcomes and extracting the required information to make the required decisions that further helps in reaching the conclusion of the study towards vital hypothesized relationships.

Figure 1 Evaluation of Structural Model

Table 1 demonstrates the results structural model in order to test direct hypothesis. The findings of this study indicated that all alternative hypothesis are supported. The findings indicated that reliability, security and website design has positive and significant link with trust variable. Furthermore, hypothesis four is also supported as it indicates that trust has significant and positive relationship with loyalty. The same information has also been thus offered through figure-1, in order to produce the desired information about the potential relationships toward the phenomenal connection to reach the desired results and reaching the conclusion.

Table 1 Direct Hypothesis Testing

H1-4	Link	SB	SE	TV	PV	2.50%	97.50%	Decision	R2	f2	Q2
H1	RL -> TR	0.225	0.076	2.904	0.000	0.044	0.340	Supported	0.406	0.046	0.248
H2	SC -> TR	0.354	0.081	4.308	0.000	0.207	0.525	Supported		0.125	
H3	WD -> TR	0.198	0.074	2.628	0.000	0.054	0.343	Supported		0.036	
H4	TR -> LO	0.692	0.062	13.233	0.000	0.558	0.763	Supported	0.450	0.869	0.300

Table 2 validates that there is significant and mediating effect between observed variables. More specifically, table indicated that trust has significant mediating relationship between that reliability and loyalty. Similarly, the trust has significant mediating relationship between that security and loyalty. Lastly, trust has significant mediating relationship between that website design and loyalty. In conclusion, all hypothesis is supported as per the results of the statistical procedures.

Table 2 Mediation Analysis

H5-7	Link	SB	SE	TV	PV	2.50%	97.50%	Decision
H5	RL -> TR -> LO	0.156	0.053	2.759	0.000	0.034	0.253	Supported
H6	SC -> TR -> LO	0.245	0.061	3.848	0.000	0.137	0.365	Supported
H7	WD -> TR -> LO	0.144	0.053	2.548	0.000	0.035	0.254	Supported

CONCLUSION

The impact of guerilla marketing on brand loyalty is investigated in this study. The results of the structural equation model show that the factors of guerilla marketing's influence on social media have an impact on brand loyalty. The results of this study indicated that there is a significant and positive relationship with customer loyalty and trust as a mediator has significant and positive relationship between observed variables. This study proves the following: Social media determinants of guerrilla advertising that affect the functional. It provides valuable insight for marketers and can be used to create a symbolic brand image. Marketers could benefit from these findings. Marketers can improve their brand image by developing stronger guerrilla marketing methods. Since the study was completed, this sample was considered appropriate. People who utilize social media were polled. Despite the fact that the age range of Despite the fact that university students make up majority of social media users on campus, they may not be using it to its maximum potential. Thus, everyone in the population towards future research could look into influence of guerrilla marketing from diverse perspectives in order to inspire the customers towards particular products in loyal behaviors.

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